

A Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Work Life Balance Professionals - A Conceptual Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Historically the responsibility of women should be of cooking, cleaning, raising children etc. These folks were witnessed in the form of caregiver as well as home keeper and were refused their right of entry outside home. Women nowadays have created their symbol in each and every sphere. Be it literature, arts, politics, sports, Corporate or any other sphere, women are getting ready to take up challenges. In this scenario, emotional intelligence plays a major in work life balance of women professionals. A small amount of stress can be useful tool for motivating, but excessive creates problem both professionally and personally. So people should be emotionally balanced and they should aware of how to manage the situations well emotionally. The purpose of this study is to find out the positive association between emotional intelligence and work life balance of women professionals. Researcher has diverted to study this with the help of secondary data. The research study found that employees with high EI have got a higher overall work life balance compared to employees with low EI.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, work life balance, women professionals*

Introduction

Changes in the social, political and economic fabric of societies have influenced and continue to influence both the nature of employment and its relationship to life outside work. Women and Work Life Balance Times are changing from traditional where the husband earned, and the wife stayed at home to the

modern when the husband earns and the wife earns too. But the wife still cooks, washes and runs the house. Although women have started spreading her wings in all spheres of life but the traditional concept of the women as the homemaker has not gone away from people's mind. So, today's women are striving continuously for "Work Life Balance".

As the concept "Emotional intelligence" became popular and many earlier researches have agreed on the fact that EQ helps person to achieve success in his personal and professional life. The components of Emotional intelligence helps to recognize, understand and manage ones and others emotions through self actualization, empathy, social awareness and relationship management. Emotional intelligence plays a significant role in the organizations as well as in personal life of people. it helps individual to understand one's own strengths and weaknesses. The field of study is focusing on the role of emotional intelligence in managing Work-Life Balance. Work-Life Balance consist many aspects, these can be social factors, working environment, type of job, job satisfaction, family background and life stages etc.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence means an individual's ability to recognize and understand the emotions of one's as well as for others. A person who has a high emotional intelligence is aware of the fact that an emotion affects every aspect of human life in personal or professional.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is the capacity of individuals to recognize their own, and other people's emotions, to discriminate between different feelings and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior. (Coleman, Andrew 2008). Emotional Intelligence (EI) is a term that describes the ability, capability, skill or a self-perceived knowledge to recognize, assess, and deal with the emotions of one's self and of others. According to Daniel Goleman "Emotional Intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing our own feelings & those of others, for motivating ourselves and for managing emotions well in ourselves and our relationships." (Goleman, 1998).

Work Life Balance

Work-life balance is a concept including proper prioritizing between "work" (career and ambition) and "lifestyle" (health, pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development/meditation). Related, though broader, terms include "lifestyle calm balance" and "lifestyle choices". Work-life balance, in its broadest sense, is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or 'fit' between the multiple roles in a person's life (Hudson, 2005).

As already stated before Work life balance is not equal balance between work and personal activities. Life is and should be more flexible than this. Our work life balance will vary from time to time, it may often vary day to day. What is right balance for today may be different tomorrow. The right balances when we are single will be different when we get married or if we get children. So work life balance will be different at different quadrants of life on the basis of priorities. Our aim will be the fullest achievement and enjoyment in all our spheres of life. The sporadic focus on career advancement, time-consuming child care, responsibility for family life, and a woman's tendency toward understatement were barriers to career development. Work-family enrichment has a positive spillover effect that spreads positive energy and helps to balance the work-life relationship. For each individual, the allocation and interaction of different resources such as time, money, scope of decision making, and physical, emotional, and social resources, were essential to maintain the individual work-life balance.

Objective

- To study the relationship between the Emotional Intelligence and work life balance of women professionals
- To study the positive association of work life balance with emotional intelligence.

Literature Review

A systematic literature review was conducted by a researcher. Various research papers, books, journals and authentic websites were referred for this purpose. Research papers selected for this research are summarized as follows:-

Rebecca Bundhun quotes in The National (2009), an Abu Dhabi National Paper that Women and men generally have a different perception of what the "life" part of the balance involves. For women it tends to be devoting more time to family, while for men it is spending more time pursuing personal interests.

Murphy and Doherty (2011) revealed that it is not possible to measure work-life balance in an absolute way as there are personal circumstances which influence the way that is perceived but establishing a harmony that reflects an individual's priorities whereas employees must draw a firm line between their home and work lives and be confident that the line is in the right place

Loy (2005) examined the career paths of women financial executives who had tried various approaches to balancing career and family. The professional level these women had attained requires a huge commitment of time, energy, and emotion that looked natural to employers and clients, who assume that a career deserves single-minded allegiance. Meanwhile, these women must confront the cultural model of family that defined marriage and motherhood as a woman's primary vocation. The above study focused on the social and cultural forces that created women's identities and shaped their understanding of what made life, worth living.

Sekar (2014) Work-life balance is a broad concept including proper prioritizing between "work" which means career and ambition on one hand and "life" which means health, pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development on the other. It is otherwise called as "Life style balance" or "life balance". It does not mean that 50: 50 proportion that is 50% for work

and another 50% for life. It means that how one managing their work and personal life properly without any problem/ trouble. This research paper examined the work life balance amongst employees of garment units in Tirupur district. The methodology adopted for the study was descriptive research design. Data were collected from 100 employees through questionnaire method. In the present study, statistical tools such as percentage analysis and chi-square were used for the analysis. The results indicated that the work life balance of employees are not completely successful due to their present working hours, working environment and lack of time for family and personal growth, work load, responsibilities in work and decrease of job security due to recession, stress, lack of entertainment etc.,

Sakthi Suganya. R et al in (2010) , proposed that Organization's success depends on people and they have multiple responsibilities, diverse needs and often conflict priorities. The work life balance analysis of managers helps to know about the managers' working conditions, environment, and their present situation of balancing their personal life with work. Based on the analysis, the present study concluded that the work life balance of managers is not completely successful. The negative impact of the recession is not only reflected in the IT sector, also it will affect the garment industry in future due to the changes in dollar values, increase in products prices, work load, responsibilities in work, decreasing of job security. Hence, organizations must ensure that there is a work life balance to their organizations, which will pave the way for better performance, improved morale and results in higher job satisfaction, which will ultimately help to improve the organization's performance and profitability.

Good work life balance is more important for women than for men as she has to manage home and office at a time as she is the real home maker. A new Global research by Accenture a consulting firm found that around 70% of female respondent in India think that WLB is the key to their definition of "success" in their career while only 40% of men felt that they quit their job because of long or inflexible working hours for women that figure was 48% and almost 50-55% of the women are struggling to achieve work life balance and while doing the same they felt the stress which affect their physical and mental health as stress is simply a

reaction to a stimulus that disturbs our physical or mental equilibrium.

CONCLUSION

Individuals and organizations are required to work together to accomplish work life balance. It has been found that the study indicates a higher level of EI leads to better work life balance and Emotional intelligence is an effective way to integrate, enhance and provide better work and family life. With the help this study it's concluded that the emotional intelligence has greater impact on the employee's performance and EI Organization which is based on organizational strategy & it improve business performance. Corporate world should focus on formulating, developing, implementing, maintaining better work life balance policies in order to build sustainable and enriching organization. They should come up with effective and efficient working culture that supports the use of available policies which will also a great importance. This can mechanically bring down the work pressure, grievances and also dispute among the employee so they are able to really focus much more on their excellence as well as productive work and at the same time they will certainly balance their work life which will enhance the individuals as well as organizational overall performance.

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